

Cost and composition of aketons and pourpoints in the English accounts, 1209-1235 AD

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Seals of Kings John (1199) and Henry III (1219)

Introduction

A considerable fraction of the mentions of armour in the English accounts from the reigns of John and William III touch upon the textile armours, including aketons and gambesons. The quantitative information on the kind and amount of cloth and raw cotton used for the making of the textile armours, and the cost of labour, paves way to improved understanding of such equipment which remains almost completely hidden from view in the visual arts. This article treats only the records that are descriptive of the cost or structure of these armours, excluding the more general mentions, and aims to present the newly discovered data on early 13th century English aketons and pourpoints in a systematic manner.

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1. Aketons

1.1 Aketon for Henry Fitzduke (1209)

The Misae Roll of 1209 records details of one aketon ordered for Henry Fitzduke. “For 7 ells of linen fabric for the aketon of Henry son of the duke, and for cotton for the same aketon, 3

shillings 7 pennies” (*pro 7 ulnis linee tele ad faciendum unum alcotone, ... & pro cotone ad illum alcotone 3s. 7d*).

Just a little below in the same Roll, we find the price of 6 pounds of cotton: for 30 pounds of cotton, 15 shillings, meaning one pound of cotton then cost half a shilling, or 6 pennies.

From a Close Rolls record of 1208, have the price of linen cloth used by the King, "1 mark for 32 ells of linen cloth for lining the lord King's arming tunics". Therefore, linen fabric cost 5 d./ell, which makes for 7 ells, 2s 11 d.

The price for 1 linen aketon, not covered with silk, was 3 s 7 d., as we saw above, which includes 2s 11 d. for linen cloth, leaving a remainder of 8 d. - about the price of 1.3 pounds of cotton.

The above price 3 s 7 d. does not include the price of silk covering.

1.2. King John's aketon (1212-1213)

The 1212-1213 Misae Roll contains one of the most specific and valuable records on aketons: "1.5 pounds of cotton for a king's aketon (*auketon*) worth 12 d., and the sewing of the same aketon, 12 d." This tells exactly how much raw cotton an aketon contained, and how much the work cost. The price of cotton here (8 d. per pound) is significantly higher than in 1.1, which can be related to the market prices, or that King preferred the cotton of a higher quality than that bought for Henry Fitzduke.

1.3 Silk covering for an aketon (1223)

Henry III made his own large order of cloth for clothing and textile armours in 1223. That included: "Credit to the same for one [length of] Arras brocade for our cuisses and spaulders and also for covering an aketon for our use, 20 shillings". Although we are given the total of brocade for the covering of tree items, the aketon would have used roughly half of the total brocade cloth, worth 10 shillings.

1.4. Aketon covered with silk (1235)

A 1235 entry in the Miscellanea of the Chancery supplies this: "*ad ij alkethon' cend[allo] cooperiendas...*" - "two aketons covered with cendal".

2. Pourpoints

2.1 King John's pourpoint (1208)

In 1208, King John ordered a considerable amount of material for his arming needs: "4 pounds 17 shillings for 143 ells of rancia [orange-coloured cloth] for making King's pourpoint; ... 3 shillings for accurate point making". The two parts of the record are separate, but we can

hypothesize that the “point/hole making” refers to the same pourpoint, as no other gamboised armours are mentioned; besides, the specific word (*pungte*) is rare and has a common root with “perpunctus”.

2.2 John’s light pourpoint (1215)

A light pourpoint was mentioned in 1215 (*levibus perpunctus*), probably relating to the lesser than usual thickness resulting from a smaller number of fabric layers.

2.3 A pourpoint worth 10 s. (1212-1213)

A pourpoint was given as a gift for king’s servant, and is specifically said to have cost 10 shillings, as testified by the Misae Roll of that year.

2.4 Pourpoint of black cendal (1224)

Upon Falk de Breaute’s exile in 1224, and inventory of his armours was drafted in the Curia Regis Roll, including: “de lineis armaturis: j purpunctum et j espauleram de nigro cendalo”. Falk’s pourpoint was therefore covered with black or dark-coloured cendal cloth. However, it is worth noting that here, as in some other records, the pourpoint is summarized under *lineis armaturis*, i.e. “linen armours”, which may be a generic term for soft armours and doesn’t necessitate the use of the linen in them.

3. Discussion

Aketons were kept clearly distinct from pourpoints in the English bureaucratic accounts. The clerks strived to be clear and systematic, and have probably struck to a consistent naming conventions in armour-related matters, as elsewhere. The above evidence suggests this indeed was the case. Aketons are said to be made of linen cloth, quilted and stuffed with raw cotton, while pourpoints are gamboised garments made of many layers of cloth, probably without a filling. The 143 ells of cloth would definitely be a very thick protection alleviating the need for extra padding provided by raw cotton. Aketons probably used a single or double layer of linen, which served as a shell for raw cotton; the higher nobility preferred them being covered with costly silk, which could cost about 10 shillings in cloth. A pourpoint possibly required much more sewing work than an aketon (3 shillings vs. 1 shilling, see Sections 2.1 and 1.2). As a result, a lordly pourpoint seems to have cost considerably more than an aketon, due to both the expenses in cloth and work. At the same time, the difference in the cost of a lordly pourpoint (2.1) and servant’s pourpoint (2.3) is 10-fold or more, resulting from the use of cheaper cloth in the servant’s armour, and possibly from the smaller thickness of the garment.

Table 1. Summary of the data on aketons and pourpoints in the discussed records. The entries marked with grey are my extrapolations and calculations.

	year	Amount of cloth/raw cotton	Cost of cloth/ raw cotton	Cost of work	Total cost
Aketons					
1.1	1209	7 ells of linen 1.3 pounds of raw cotton	2s. 11 d. 8 d.		3s. 7d
1.2	1212- 1213	1.5 pounds of raw cotton for an aketon 7 ells of linen	12 d. 2s. 11 d.	12 d. = 1 s.	4 s. 11 s.
1.3	1223	Brocade of Arras covering for an aketon 7 ells of linen 1.5 pounds of raw cotton	approx. 10 s. 2s. 11 d. 12 d.	12 d.	14 s. 11 d.
1.4	1235	Aketon covered with cendal			
Pourpoints					
2.1	1208	143 ells of rancia	4 pounds 17 s.	3 s. for “point making”	at least 5 pounds
2.2	1215	“Light pourpoint”			
2.3	1212- 1213	Pourpoint for king’s servant			10 s.
2.4	1224	Pourpoint covered with black cendal			

References

1.1

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